

LEARNING RECHNOLOGIES RESEARCH WITH PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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In this section of the chapter, we examine research that has attempted language teaching and learning. However, this is no straightforward task. The fundamental aims in research studies can vary significantly. To understand this difference, Ware and Hellmich draw a helpful distinction between learning technologies studies that focus on learning focused studies attempt to identify to what extent technologies might outcomes and studies that focus on learning opportunities. Outcomes- lead to specific measurable gains in second language learning. As such, they tend to be more narrowly focused and to rely mainly on quantitative research methods. Opportunities-focused studies are more exploratory in nature and attempt to gauge to what extent technologies might support language learning in a more general sense-for example, by providing increased opportunities for language practice in informal out-of-school contexts.

As such, researchers in these studies tend to take a wider-often sociolinguistic or ecological perspective and to rely mainly on qualitative research methods. Of course, these research orientations are not mutually exclusive, and one can find studies in which both research approaches can be identified. When reviewing research studies into learning technologies and language learning, we also need to keep in mind that what may be a successful small-scale research project in one context may be less successful in another context. In a world of increasingly complex technologies being used in increasingly complex environments and interactions, it becomes difficult to say that technology x will always produce language learning result y; the range of factors involved in any learning situation is simply too varied. As Thomas et al. point out, it is important to realize that: merely referencing success with small-scale projects and arguing that they can be generalized and applied in uniform ways across language learning environments is no longer feasible.

CALL technologies do not provide a panacea for all of the challenges facing language learners and educators; integration cannot be seamless, nor can it be applied by all language educators in all contexts. In addition, not all research studies are firmly grounded in theory. For example, in a review of 43 empirical research studies into Web 2.0 tools in a number of learning technology journals and books, Wang and Vásquez found that over half of the studies-56 percent-did not have an identifiable theoretical foundation. They also found that several of the studies suffered from common methodological weaknesses, such as convenience sampling of participants, rather than random sampling or purposeful sampling. They pointed out that in K-12 contexts, this was often due to logistical issues such as controlled access to minors or the need to work with already formed groups of students in individual classrooms. Wang and Vásquez also identified a general shift in these research studies from primarily quantitative approaches to data collection to an emphasis on qualitative data. However, they pointed out that some research studies failed to carry out in-depth analyses of qualitative data, such as exploring students' perspectives to help explain observed phenomena. Another weakness they identified stemmed from the techno-centric view taken by some researchers, in which the technology alone was held to account for

learning, without consideration for the wider pedagogical context-such a teaching strategies or instructional materials.

With these caveats in mind, we will examine both small-scale research point to measurable gains in language learning, while in other cases, results studies and larger studies. As we will see, in some cases research findings are mixed. As we have discussed previously in this volume, comparing the results of research studies is problematic, even when a single technology such as cell phones, or a single tool, such as blogs, is used, given the wide range of contextual factors involved in learning that go well beyond the technology in question. Also, given the scope of this volume, we need to limit our review of learning technologies research to a number of key or significant examples, so for each of the research areas identified in this section, we look at two or three studies. Nevertheless, by reviewing a range research approaches, agendas, and tools that make up the rich body of studies, we hope to give the reader an understanding of the different learning technologies research.

We divide this section into research studies that focus on vocabulary acquisition, followed by studies that address the four skills: reading because researchers themselves are often concerned with exploring gains in writing, listening, and speaking. We choose this division for the studies these specific language areas. We finish the section by taking a brief look newer online spaces for collaboration, such as virtual worlds, and what this might mean for primary school students' language acquisition.

Research into Vocabulary Acquisition

As with the majority of learning technologies research, most of the studies into vocabulary acquisition have taken place in secondary school and university contexts. However, there is some research into vocabulary acquisition with younger students, particularly with mobile devices. As cell phones, smartphones, and tablets become increasingly available and affordable, and with their rich multimedia capabilities and additional features such as GPS tracking, some recent studies have examined how these devices might support vocabulary acquisition for primary school students. Generally speaking, research into language acquisition with mobile devices can be divided into two categories: content-based research and design-oriented research. Content-based research focuses on digital content that is delivered via mobile devices, whereas design-oriented research examines the learning experience that can be facilitated by the use of a mobile device, often in out-of-class socially oriented contexts. The portability of mobile devices means that they can easily be used both inside and outside the classroom, providing opportunities for learners to take part in language learning tasks in informal, real-life contexts-often referred to as 'situated' learning contexts.

Because lexis can provide a finite set of items for students to acquire, several research studies into the use of mobile devices to support vocabulary acquisition take a content-based approach, with words or idioms presented to students via the devices, for example as key words, phrases, or quizzes, possibly in the form of flashcards or regular SMS messages. Students' acquisition of the lexis is then tested (for example, see studies with adults by Thornton & Houser, Levy & Kennedy, see also our review of content-based vocabulary studies based on SMS messages with secondary school students). In contrast to this approach, a design- the use of mobile devices in a primary school is described in Classroom oriented study examining how vocabulary learning can be supported by the use of mobile devices in a primary school is described in Classroom.

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